

Aalto University
Department of Physics

Sandpile Experiment

Antti J. Nurminen

Oiva Kunnamo

Report by: *Antti J. Nurminen*

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Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	Summary	2
3	Model and Relevant Physics	3
3.1	Self-Organized Criticality	3
3.2	Related Physics and Observations	4
4	Methodology	4
4.1	Testing apparatus	4
4.2	Computational model	6
4.3	Initialized parameters	6
5	Results	6
5.1	Pile mass	6
5.2	Probability Distributions	8
5.3	Critical Angles	10
5.4	Reliability	11
5.5	Simulation and Measurements	12
6	Conclusion	12
7	References	14

1 Introduction

This experiment investigates self-organized criticality (SOC) through the dynamics of a sandpile under continuous sand flow. SOC describes how certain systems naturally evolve to a critical state without external fine-tuning. In the context of a sandpile, avalanches of varying sizes occur when the system reaches a critical angle. The experiment measured mass fluctuations and avalanche distributions on circular platforms of different sizes. A computational model was also used in order to simulate the system and compare theoretical and experimental results.

2 Summary

The experiment confirmed key characteristics of SOC, demonstrating that the sandpile fluctuates around a critical angle, leading to avalanches that follow a power-law distribution. Larger platforms exhibited greater variation in avalanche sizes, while increased sand flow reduced this variance. The computational model supported these findings but showed deviations due to simplified assumptions. Despite minor discrepancies, the results align with SOC theory, providing insights into the behavior of critical systems in nature.

3 Model and Relevant Physics

3.1 Self-Organized Criticality

Self-organized criticality (SOC) is a theoretical concept that explains the way certain systems can evolve towards a critical state naturally, without having any external fine-tuning to its parameters. Self-organized criticality causes the system to evolve to the critical state, after which it fluctuates around that point. Unlike traditional systems SOC-systems have the critical point as an attractor, meaning that over time the system tends to evolve towards the critical point regardless of the starting conditions. [1] [2]

Critical point refers to a state of the system, where a very small alteration of some of its parameters can lead to a change in the state of any possible size. This means that after evolving beyond the critical state the change of state can be anything from unnoticeable to very large. It has been observed that the distribution of multiple reorganizations due reaching the critical point follows a power law (or $1/f$) function. [5]

The sandpile experiment, that this lab report discusses, provides an intuitive example of the self-organizing criticality phenomena. When sand grains are slowly added to the pile, it reaches a critical angle, for which avalanches of varying sizes can occur. Each added sand grain may or may not trigger an avalanche around the critical point, so the system is in a metastable state. When observing the sizes of repeated avalanches by having the pile under a constant sand flow and letting the pile fluctuate around the critical point, a power-law distribution of the sizes of the avalanches can be recognized. [3] [4]

3.2 Related Physics and Observations

The concept of the angle of repose is an important aspect of the theoretical model of the sand pile experiment. It describes the steepest possible slope the pile can withstand, before an avalanche occurs. This attribute isn't a constant, so it does not describe the exact critical point, but rather the probability for an avalanche to occur. When the pile fluctuates around the critical point the observed angle of repose changes with every avalanche, averaging out to a certain value over time. [3]

The self organized criticality property related to the sandpile experiment is relevant in many other physical phenomena. When single grains are added to the pile, very small changes in the systems configuration occurs. However, when reaching the critical slope a very large reorganization of the pile can occur, a phenomena commonly observed with avalanches and earthquakes. [3] [4]

Also the appearance of the power-law distribution of avalanche sizes is an interesting and not at all trivial observation. Many other natural systems follow a Gaussian distribution, which could be expected to apply to the sand pile experiment. The specific properties of the distribution depends on factors such as grain shape and friction. [1] [2]

4 Methodology

4.1 Testing apparatus

This lab-experiment aims to study the mass fluctuations of a sandpile on a elevated circular platform under a constant sand flow. The test apparatus is prepared by first leveling the high-precision scale, using a bubble level. Then the circular plate of the wanted size is chosen and placed on top of the scale and the scale is zeroed. A conical shield is then placed on top of the scale

so that the sand falling from the platform doesn't drop on the scale. After this a funnel nozzle size is chosen, to regulate the steady sand flow to the platform. The experiment is conducted in a total of three times using two different funnel- and platform sizes.

The picture 1 shows the testing apparatus:

Figure 1: A diagram of the testing apparatus [5]

The measurement begins by starting the data recording from the computer connected to the scale. Then the sand consisting of glass beads is deposited to the funnel, beginning the flow with constant rate. Using the flow as a reference the circular platform is moved so that the sand flow is concentrated on its center.

As the pile grows, it eventually reaches a critical slope causing an avalanche, the mass of which is recorded with the scale. The pile is being held under the constant sand flow for several minutes, during which it fluctuates around the critical point. A visual height inspection of the sandpile is done using a ruler. This can be used to compare the observed and calculated critical angle. When enough datapoints have been measured, containing multiple avalanches, the experiment is ended.

4.2 Computational model

A cellular automaton (CA) model is used to simulate the behaviour of a sandpile. The model represents the sandpile as a two-dimensional grid, where each cell takes the value of the height of the sandpile at that position. The simulation works by dropping individual grains on the grid randomly, with a bias towards the center. This simulates the fact that in the real experiment the sand is dropped to the center of the platform. In both cases this leads to a conical sandpile. When the simulation self-organizes into a critical state, an avalanche occurs, which size is determined by the power law. This is a simplified model, that describes the real experiment quite well.

4.3 Initialized parameters

The measurements were done three times in total, for two platform sizes and two nozzle sizes. The initialized parameters are shown in table 1:

Measurement number	1	2	3
Nozzle diameter (mm)	5	5	8
Platform diameter (mm)	100	160	160
Bead diameter (mm)	0.4-0.8	0.4-0.8	0.4-0.8

Table 1: Initialized parameters for the three measurements

5 Results

5.1 Pile mass

The raw data consists of the mass of the pile. Given the known frequency of the scale data collection, the mass can be shown as a function of time. The functions show the whole time interval, and a zoomed picture that shows the mass fluctuations and the avalanche behavior. In the following pictures: ND = Nozzle Diameter and PD = Platform Diameter

Figure 2: ND=5mm, PD=100mm

Figure 3: ND=5mm, PD=160mm

Figure 4: ND=8mm, PD=160mm

Figure 5: Simulation

We can note from pictures 2 and 3 that the system reaches the critical point much quicker and the relative sizes of the avalanches are much smaller with the smaller plate, as expected. We can also note that the variation between individual avalanche sizes seems to be larger with the larger plate. However, from picture 4 we can see that, with the larger plate and the larger nozzle the system reaches the critical point much quicker (due to the increased sand flow) and avalanches seem to be happening on a large frequency, while having some variation. The simulation data in picture 5 indicates a more idealized formation of avalanches, where the changes in mass are almost instantaneous.

5.2 Probability Distributions

The probability distributions shows the distribution of avalanche sizes for each experiment. The distributions are shown as both PDF (Probability distribution function) and CDF (Cumulative distribution function) forms. All of the functions are plotted with both linear and log-log scale, because of the power law distributions. For the PDF-plots in the log-log scale a linear fit is performed, to indicate the exponent in the distribution.

Figure 6: ND=5mm, PD=100mm

Figure 7: ND=5mm, PD=100mm

Figure 8: ND=5mm, PD=160mm

Figure 9: ND=5mm, PD=160mm

Figure 10: ND=8mm, PD=160mm

Figure 11: ND=8mm, PD=160mm

Figure 12: Simulation

Figure 13: Simulation

Comparing the data from figures 6 and 7 with the data from figures 8 and 9, we can confirm, that avalanches follow a power-law like distribution (the probability is concentrated close to the smallest possible value). We also note that the variance of the avalanches is greater with a larger plate. This is also reflected on the exponent form the log-log linear fit: 1.37 for the smaller plate and 1.2 for the larger one. The same conclusion can be made from the cumulative distribution functions as well. This means that with the smaller plate a large majority of avalanches are very small and bigger avalanches are very unlikely. For the larger plate larger avalanches are much more likely.

Comparing the data from figures 8 and 9 with the data from figures 10 and 11, we see that increasing the flow rate with a larger nozzle, decreases the variance of the avalanche sizes. This can be seen from the wider distribution as well as from the exponent from the linear fit: 1.2 for the smaller nozzle and 1.53 for the larger nozzle. This means that with the larger nozzle a large

majority of avalanches are very small and bigger avalanches are much more unlikely than with the smaller nozzle.

From the data of the simulation in figure 12 and 13, we can see that the distribution follows the most closely the power law; the log-log distribution is closest to being linear. We can also note that the variance of the distribution is the closest to the measurement done with the smallest nozzle and plate.

The observed probability distributions of avalanche sizes align with the explanations in Reference [4], which describes how SOC systems exhibit power-law behavior. In our results, smaller plates resulted in a steeper probability distribution, (large avalanches were less frequent), while larger plates allowed for a broader range of avalanche sizes, which is consistent with Reference [4]. Additionally, increasing the flow rate through a larger nozzle led to a narrower distribution, with a higher frequency of small avalanches. This matches the theoretical expectation that higher input rates reduce the time for system-wide reorganizations, limiting the occurrence of larger avalanches.

5.3 Critical Angles

The critical angles and angles of repose derived from the data are listed in table 2:

	Critical angle (deg)	Angle of repose (deg)
ND=5mm, PD=100mm	22.7	23.2
ND=5mm, PD=160mm	22.4	23.0
ND=8mm, PD=160mm	22.3	23.0
Simulation	17.4	17.9

Table 2: The critical angles and angles of repose for each measurement

For the larger plate and larger nozzle the measured critical angle was approximated to be around 20 degrees, which is consistent with the calculated angle. The calculated critical angles (22.3–22.7) and angles of repose (23.0–23.2) show pretty consistent behavior across experiments, with lower values observed in the simulation (17.4 and 17.9). Reference [4] describes how sand-

piles in self-organized criticality (SOC) fluctuate around a metastable critical point, where small perturbations can either cause minimal rearrangements or trigger large avalanches. This aligns with our results.

Variations in avalanche size between setups are influenced by platform size and flow rate, as seen in the probability distributions. Smaller platforms exhibit larger avalanche variability, while larger nozzles produce more frequent but smaller avalanches.

The lower angles in the simulation suggest that real-world factors like grain friction and granular interactions contribute to steeper angles in physical sandpiles. Despite minor deviations, the experiment supports SOC theory and aligns well with Reference [4].

5.4 Reliability

All of the experiments show properties of self organized criticality. The results also show a power-law like distribution, which is not perfect however. From the log-log scale, we can see that the distribution is initially almost flat for smaller avalanche sizes. Then for a certain section the avalanches the distribution decreases linearly, and flattens out towards the end. This clashes with the expected power-law distribution, which the simulation follows much more closely. I suspect that this is due to the geometry of the sand piles as well as the grain shape. Another factor is the measurement accuracy of the scale. It is not able to accurately measure very small avalanches, which can result in unreliable results with the smallest detected avalanches. These factors make the results differ from the idealized version of the simulation, where SOC-properties are shown more clearly.

In general the the reliability and accuracy of the measurement was such that the SOC-properties of the sandpile experiment can be seen, but the results do not exactly follow the hypothesis. Sources of error include the accuracy

and the calibration of the scale (for very small avalanches), positioning of the platform/plate and the angle of the plate. In a better controlled environment these could be set more accurately.

5.5 Simulation and Measurements

The cellular automaton simulation and the real experiment share some of the key elements such as: exhibiting self organized criticality, avalanches follow approximately a power-law distribution and the pile is stabilized near the critical slope. However, some differences with the real sandpile and the simulation are caused from the limitations of the simulation such as: dynamics of the grains and granular interactions, friction and energy dissipation. Also the limited grid resolution does not reflect the real world, where the grains don't have discrete positions.

The differences are visible with the plotted graphs; the simulation shows almost instantaneous avalanches and the distribution follows the power law much closer, than with the real experiments.

6 Conclusion

This study examined the behavior of a sandpile under continuous sand flow to investigate self-organized criticality (SOC). By measuring avalanche sizes and mass fluctuations on circular plates of different sizes, we explored how the system stabilizes near a critical angle and exhibits power-law avalanche distributions. A computational model was also used to simulate the sandpile dynamics, providing a comparison between experimental and theoretical expectations.

The results confirmed some key characteristics of SOC, with the sandpile fluctuating around a state where avalanches of varying sizes occurred. The probability distributions followed a power-law trend, as expected, with larger

plates showing greater variance. The critical angles and angles of repose were consistent across experiments, though deviations were observed in the simulation. This is possibly due to the assumptions made with the simulation.

I learned about the concept of self organized criticality as a whole. I understood the theoretical and mathematical basis behind the sandpile experiment relating to power-law distributions. I also learned about the broader physical applications around SOC, such as avalanche dynamics, forest fires and earthquake prediction. Generally studying SOC in these contexts could lead to improved predictive models and a better understanding of large-scale dynamic systems in nature.

To improve our understanding, future work could refine both the experimental and computational aspects of the study. Experimentally, using higher-resolution scales or different granular materials with varying frictional properties. In simulations, incorporating more realistic interactions such as interactions between individual grains and energy dissipation could enhance the accuracy of the model.

7 References

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